

```
1  singlewell()
2  if(1)
3  //Setting the parameters for Star features
4  set(RequestContainer=cnt(
5      bArea=0,
6
7      // Which morphology properties on Original image
8      bOrigAxial=1,
9      bOrigInten=0, // use of intensity is not recommended
10     bOrigProfile=1,
11     bOrigRadial=1,
12     bOrigSymm=1,
13     bOrigThresh=1,
14
15     // Which morphology properties on Parabola filtered image
16     bSPAxial=0,
17     bSPInten=0,
18     bSPProfile=0,
19     bSPRadial=0,
20     bSPSymm=0,
21     bSPThresh=0,
22
23     // Which texture features we take
24     bBright=0,
25     bDark=0,
26     bEdge=0,
27     bHole=0,
28     bRidge=0,
29     bSaddle=0,
30     bSpot=0,
31     bValley=0,
32
33     // Which morphology properties on texture filtered images
```

```
34     bTextuAxial=0,
35     bTextuInten=0,
36     bTextuProfile=0,
37     bTextuRadial=0,
38     bTextuSymm=0,
39     bTextuThresh=0,
40
41     // How to calculate mass center
42     CenterMode="Original", // Not original: Sliding Parabola used
43
44     // optional
45     ProfileDistance=10.0, // default=10
46
47     // Normalize texture filter
48     NormalizationMode="kernel", // Values: "kernel", "none"
49     TextureScale=0.5, // default=0.5
50
51     ParabolaCurvature=10,
52
53
54 ))
55 End()
56 if(1)
57 set(RequestContainerAxial=cnt(
58     bArea=0,
59
60     // Which morphology properties on Original image
61     bOrigAxial=1,
62     bOrigInten=0, // use of intensity is not recommended
63     bOrigProfile=0,
64     bOrigRadial=0,
65     bOrigSymm=0,
66     bOrigThresh=0,
```

```
67
68 // Which morphology properties on Parabola filtered image
69 bSPAxial=0,
70 bSPInten=0,
71 bSPProfile=0,
72 bSPRadial=0,
73 bSPSymm=0,
74 bSPThresh=0,
75
76 // Which texture features we take
77 bBright=0,
78 bDark=0,
79 bEdge=0,
80 bHole=0,
81 bRidge=0,
82 bSaddle=0,
83 bSpot=0,
84 bValley=0,
85
86 // Which morphology properties on texture filtered images
87 bTextuAxial=0,
88 bTextuInten=0,
89 bTextuProfile=0,
90 bTextuRadial=0,
91 bTextuSymm=0,
92 bTextuThresh=0,
93
94 // How to calculate mass center
95 CenterMode="Original", // Not original: Sliding Parabola used
96
97 // optional
98 ProfileDistance=10.0, // default=10
99
```

```
100 // Normalize texture filter
101 NormalizationMode="kernel", // Values: "kernel", "none"
102 TextureScale=0.5, // default=0.5
103
104 ParabolaCurvature=10,
105
106
107 ))
108 End()
109
110 if(1)
111 set(RequestContainerVesicles=cnt(
112     bArea=0,
113
114     // Which morphology properties on Original image
115     bOrigAxial=0,
116     bOrigInten=0, // use of intensity is not recommended
117     bOrigProfile=1,
118     bOrigRadial=0,
119     bOrigSymm=1,
120     bOrigThresh=1,
121
122     // Which morphology properties on Parabola filtered image
123     bSPAxial=0,
124     bSPInten=0,
125     bSPProfile=1,
126     bSPRadial=0,
127     bSPSymm=0,
128     bSPThresh=0,
129
130     // Which texture features we take
131     bBright=1,
132     bDark=1,
```

```
133     bEdge=1,
134     bHole=1,
135     bRidge=1,
136     bSaddle=1,
137     bSpot=1,
138     bValley=1,
139
140     // Which morphology properties on texture filtered images
141     bTextuAxial=0,
142     bTextuInten=1,
143     bTextuProfile=1,
144     bTextuRadial=1,
145     bTextuSymm=1,
146     bTextuThresh=1,
147
148     // How to calculate mass center
149     CenterMode="Original", // Not original: Sliding Parabola used
150
151     // optional
152     ProfileDistance=10.0, // default=10
153
154     // Normalize texture filter
155     NormalizationMode="kernel", // Values: "kernel", "none"
156     TextureScale=0.5, // default=0.5
157
158     ParabolaCurvature=10,
159
160
161     ))
162 End()
163
164
165 // Prepare multifield images
```

```
166 input(IN_ImageField, 0, "Image Field", "i", "Number of the image field to analyze. If set to 0 all
167 image fields of the well get processed.")
168 OperaTemplates::ControllImages()
169
170 // Channels info
171 input(NumberOfChannels, 3, "Number of Channels:Channels", "i", "Number of channels
172 recorded in each field")
173
174 input(IN_ChanNuc, 1, "Channel for Nucleus Detection:Channels", "i", "if not available use 0")
175 input(IN_ChanCyto, 4, "Channel for Cytoplasm Detection:Channels", "i", "if not available use 0")
176 input(IN_ChanMemb, 4, "Channel for Membrane Detection:Channels", "i", "if not available use
177 0")
178 input(IN_ChanActin, 0, "Channel for Actin Determination:Channels", "i", "if not available use 0")
179 input(IN_ChanDAPI, 3, "Channel for DAPI Determination:Channels", "i", "if not available use 0")
180 input(IN_ChanProt, 0, "Channel for Protrusion Determination:Channels", "i", "if not available
181 use 0")
182 input(IN_ChanYAP, 0, "Channel for YAP Determination:Channels", "i", "if not available use 0")
183
184
185 // Filtering prams
186
187 input(IN_DAPIIntensitymax, 2500, "Maximum DAPI Intensity:Filtering prameters", "i", "Allowed
188 maximum intensity, remove mitotic cells")
189 input(IN_DAPImin, 100, "Minimum DAPI:Filtering prameters")
190 input( IN_max_dist, 1, "Maximum distance of objects in a cluster:Filtering prameters",
191 description="Specifies how close or far the objects have to be in order to be considered
192 clustered. Unit: [image pixels]" )
193
194 //Output info
195 input(ShowIllustrations, yes, "Show Illustrations:Output", "b", "yes / no")
196 input(SaveImg, yes, "Save analysed cells images:Output", "y", "Save analysed cells images")
197 input(ImgPath, "C:/Opera/OperaDB/heba/BG3GFP/images/test/" , "Path to save images
198 to:Output", "p", "Path to save images to")
199 input(writesinglecell, yes, "Write Single Cell Data (need Columbus client connection):Output",
200 "b", "Write Single Cell Data ")
201
```

```

202 //H.S
203 input(DataPath, "C:/Users/acapella/Desktop/heba/nfkb/" , "Path to save data file to:Output",
204 "p", "Path to save data file")
205 input(DataFileName, "nfkb_data.txt", "Data file name:Output", "f", "Data file name")
206
207 //data_path for mac client:///Volumes/RES_ACAPELLA/OperaArchive/Heba_analysis/
208 //data path for windows client:////172.20.0.51/res_acapella/OperaArchive/Heba_analysis/
209
210 // BEGIN OF LOOP OVER IMAGE FIELDS
211 set(InvalidFields=0) //variable for counting of invalid black image fields
212 Foreach(StartField .. EndField, "_FieldCounter")
213 // Get images of current image field. Images are named IM_CH1, IM_CH2, etc.
214 //OperaTemplates::AssignChannels()
215 OperaTemplates::AssignPlane()
216 // Set images
217 set(IM_Cyto = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanCyto]) // image for cytoplasm detection
218 set(IM_Nuclei = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanNuc]) // image for nucleus detection
219 set(IM_Memb = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanMemb]) // image for nucleus detection
220 delete("stencil")
221
222 // Counting of invalid (black=unfocused) fields and termination of evaluation for these
223 if(IM_ch2.max==0)
224 set(InvalidFields=InvalidFields+1) // image fields that are invalid due to no signal intensity are
225 added to the number of invalid fields
226 else() // Start of evaluation of valid (not black) image fields
227 //multiply by ratio of crosstalk from ch3 to ch1
228
229
230
231
232 // ReSet images
233 set(IM_Cyto = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanCyto]) // image for cytoplasm detection
234 set(IM_Nuclei = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanNuc]) // image for nucleus detection

```

```
235 set(IM_Memb = _["IM_CH" & IN_ChanMemb]) // image for nucleus detection
236
237
238
239
240 //Actual object detection
241 Nuclei_Detection_Select(reference=IM_Nuclei)
242 cytoplasm_detection_select(im_cyto)
243 Cytoplasm_Detection_Select_2(im_cyto,nuclei=wholecells,Membrane=im_memb)
244
245
246
247
248 //Distance image from nucleus (the output object list will be discarded)
249 CalcZone(200,ZoneType="equidistant",objects=nuclei,Stencil=wholecells.body)
250 ZoneImage(ZoneType="OuterZones")
251 DistanceImage(OnlyUpTo100=no)
252 Rename(nuc_distanceimage=distanceimage)
253
254 //Proceed only if there are any objects
255 if (objects.count>0)
256 //Recalculate cytoplasm
257 CalcSubobjectAttributeStatistics(SubObjects=nuclei, Objects=wholecells)
258 CalcSubobjectAnalysis(SubObjects=nuclei)
259
260 SetAttr(centers,objects.borderobjectsstencil,objects=wholecells)
261 CytoplasmRegion(Stencil="body",WholeCells=objects)
262 RingRegion(Stencil="Centers")
263 SetAttr(cytoplasm,cytoplasmregion,objects=WholeCells)
264 CalcBorder(cytoplasm)
265
266 CalcArea(border)
267 CalcArea(cytoplasm)
```

```
268 CalcWidthLength()
269 calcAttr(Width2Length, "2*half_width/full_length")
270 CalcAttr("roundness")
271
272
273 //Nuclei characterization
274 CalcBorder(centers)
275 CalcArea(centers_border)
276 CalcArea(centers)
277 //save main object list
278 set(cells_obj=objects)
279 Stencil2Objects(objects.centers.image)
280 CalcWidthLength(objects)
281 CalcAttr("Width2Length",Formula=2*half_width/full_length)
282 CalcAttr("roundness")
283 CalcSubobjectAnalysis(SubObjects=objects,Objects=cells_obj)
284 CalcSubobjectStat("mean",Attribute="roundness")
285 CalcSubobjectStat("mean",Attribute="Width2Length")
286 CalcSubobjectStat("sum",Attribute="full_length")
287 CalcSubobjectStat("sum",Attribute="half_width")
288 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__length=subobj_full_length_sum)
289 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__width=subobj_half_width_sum)
290 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__roundness=subobj_roundness_mean)
291 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__NrWidth2Length=subobj_width2length_mean)
292
293
294 CalcNearestNeighbourDistance()
295
296 MembraneRegion(VisualImage=IM_cyto, stencil="Body",WholeCells =objects)
297 set(cells_obj=wholecells)
298
299 //Neighbour fraction
300 // remove the small holes and smear the outside a bit
```

```
301 Not(image=objects.index)
302 Mask2Stencil(image, Neighbourhood=8)
303 Stencil2Objects(Neighbourhood=8)
304 CalcFillStencil()
305 CalcArea()
306 ObjectFilter(area > 10)
307 Mean(Image= 9 *objects.index)
308 Mask()
309
310 Rename(nei_img=mask)
311 not(image=nei_img.image)
312 and(cells_obj.border.mask.image,image=image)
313 set(in_dilate=10)
314 Erosion(-in_dilate,image=image)
315 and(cells_obj.membraneregion.mask.image,image=image)
316 Stencil2Objects(image)
317 CalcSubobjectAnalysis(SubObjects=objects, Objects=cells_obj)
318 SetAttr(contact_region,objects.BorderObjectsStencil,objects=cells_obj)
319
320 // determine how much of our cell border is covered by the smeared outside
321 CalcStat("sum", Stencil=border, AttrName="nei_border", Image=nei_img)
322 CalcAttr("Cell__Context__NrNeighbourFraction", "1.0 - nei_border / border_area")
323
324 calcattr("nucleus__morphology__NrArea2CytoplasmArea", ( centers_area/ area))
325
326
327
328 //Mass center
329 CalcMassCentre(Weights=im_cyto)
330 CalcMassCentre(centers,Weights=im_nuclei)
331
332
```

```

333         ObjectFilter("MassCentreX==MassCentreX and MassCentreY==MassCentreY and
334 centers_MassCentreX==centers_MassCentreX and
335 centers_MassCentreY==centers_MassCentreY")
336         if (objects.count==0)
337             continue()
338         End()
339 CalcAttr(cell__morphology__CenterDistance2NucleusCenter,sqrt(((MassCentreX-
340 centers_MassCentreX)^2)+((MassCentreY-centers_MassCentreY)^2)))
341
342
343 //Zone
344 CalcZone(200,Stencil=body,ZoneType ="equidistant")
345 ZonedImage()
346 DistanceImage(OnlyUpTo100=no)
347 Rename(cyto_distanceimage=distanceimage)
348
349 //save main object list
350 set(cells_obj=objects)
351 set(unfiltered_obj=objects)
352
353 set(debug=1)
354 //////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////// Population
355 Context (before border objects )
356 if (debug==1)
357
358
359 //Remove border objects to avoid errors
360 RemoveBorderObjects()
361 //need to save cells object list between modules
362 set(cells_obj=objects)
363
364 //proceed only if there are objects
365 if (objects.count>0)
366 if (IN_ChanYap>0)

```

```
367         set(IM_yap = _["IM_CH" & IN_Chanyap])
368         RingRegion("centers",RestrictiveStencil=body,WholeCells=cells_obj,VisualImage=IM_y
369 ap)
370         CalcArea(ringregion,objects=wholecells)
371
372         calcintensity(Stencil=cytoplasm, Image=IM_yap)
373         renameattr(cytoplasm__intensity_YAP_intensity=cytoplasm_intensity)
374         calcintensity( Image=IM_yap)
375         RenameAttr(cell__intensity_YAP_intensity=intensity)
376         calcintensity(Stencil=centers, Image=IM_yap)
377         renameattr(nucleus__intensity_YAP_intensity=centers_intensity)
378         calcintensity(ringregion, IM_yap)
379         renameattr(cytoplasm_ringregion_intensity_YAP_intensity=ringregion_intensity)
380         calcattr("cell__signaling_YAP_NucbyCytoYAP",
381 nucleus__intensity_YAP_intensity/cytoplasm_ringregion_intensity_YAP_intensity)
382 set(cells_obj=objects)
383 End()
384
385
386
387 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__area=area)
388 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__Eccentricity=Eccentricity)
389 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__Border=border_area)
390 setAttr(cytoplasm__morphology__NrArea2CellArea,cytoplasm_area/cell__morphology__Area)
391 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__length=full_length)
392 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__NrWidth2Length=width2length)
393 SetAttr(cell__morphology__width, 2*half_width)
394
395 RenameAttr(cell__morphology__Roundness=roundness)
396
397 RenameAttr(cell__context__NeighbourDistance=NeighbourDistance)
398
399 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__area=centers_area)
```

```
400 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__border=centers_border_area)
401 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__NumberOfNuclei=numberofnuclei)
402 RenameAttr(nucleus__morphology__Eccentricity=centers_eccentricity)
403
404 RenameAttr(cell__coordinates__MasscentreX=MasscentreX)
405 RenameAttr(cell__coordinates__MasscentreY=MasscentreY)
406
407 //RenameAttr(plate__meta__Barcode=plate_barcode)
408 //RenameAttr(plate__meta__platename=plate_platename)
409 //RenameAttr(plate__meta__DateName=plate_dateTime)
410
411 Comment(
412 //Mitotic cells didn't work in Mar screen
413 CalcAttr(test_NucR,nucleus__morphology__roundness>.83)
414 CalcAttr(test_NucW,nucleus__morphology__width>7.8)
415 CalcAttr(test_NucT,nucleus__texture_dapi_SERdark<.01)
416 CalcAttr(test_NucA,nucleus__morphology__area>200)
417 CalcAttr(test_Mitotic,test_NucR + test_NucW + test_NucA + test_NucT)
418 CalcAttr(MitoticIndex,test_Mitotic<3)
419 )
420
421
422 //Delete the rest of the attributes
423
424 DeleteAttr(voronoi_area)
425 DeleteAttr(numberofsubobjects)
426 DeleteAttr(half_width)
427 DeleteAttr(numberofinnerobjects)
428 DeleteAttr(numberofborderobjects)
429 DeleteAttr(type)
430 DeleteAttr(vax)
431 DeleteAttr(vax2)
432 DeleteAttr(vay)
```

```
433 DeleteAttr(vay2)
434
435
436 //delete coordinates
437
438
439 DeleteAttr(centers_min_x1)
440 DeleteAttr(centers_min_x2)
441 DeleteAttr(centers_min_y1)
442 DeleteAttr(centers_min_y2)
443 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_x1)
444 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_x2)
445 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_y1)
446 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_y2)
447
448 DeleteAttr(MajorAxis)
449 DeleteAttr(MajorAxisX)
450 DeleteAttr(MajorAxisY)
451 DeleteAttr(MasscentreX)
452 DeleteAttr(MasscentreY)
453 DeleteAttr(MinorAxis)
454 DeleteAttr(MinorAxisX)
455 DeleteAttr(MinorAxisY)
456 DeleteAttr(min_x1)
457 DeleteAttr(min_x2)
458 DeleteAttr(min_y1)
459 DeleteAttr(min_y2)
460
461 DeleteAttr(centers_masscentrex)
462 DeleteAttr(centers_masscentrey)
463
464
465 DeleteAttr(mj_x1)
```

466 DeleteAttr(mj_x2)
467 DeleteAttr(mj_y1)
468 DeleteAttr(mj_y2)
469 DeleteAttr(min_1)
470 DeleteAttr(min_2)
471 DeleteAttr(mj_1)
472 DeleteAttr(mj_2)
473
474 DeleteAttr(nei_border)
475 DeleteAttr(masscentre_voronoi_area)
476
477
478 DeleteAttr(cytoplasm_area)
479 DeleteAttr(centers_majoraxis)
480 DeleteAttr(centers_majoraxisX)
481 DeleteAttr(centers_majoraxisY)
482 DeleteAttr(centers_minoraxis)
483 DeleteAttr(centers_minoraxisX)
484 DeleteAttr(centers_minoraxisY)
485 DeleteAttr(centers_min_1)
486 DeleteAttr(centers_min_2)
487 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_1)
488 DeleteAttr(centers_mj_2)
489 DeleteAttr(centers_vax)
490 DeleteAttr(centers_vax2)
491 DeleteAttr(centers_vay)
492 DeleteAttr(centers_vay2)
493 DeleteAttr(x0)
494 DeleteAttr(y0)
495
496 DeleteAttr(membraneregion_skeleton_node_count)
497 DeleteAttr(membraneregion_skeleton_border_area)
498

```

499
500
501 set(cells_obj=objects)
502
503 if (defined("all_objects"))
504     AddObjects(cells_obj, objects=all_objects, CheckOverlap=no)
505     set(all_objects=objects)
506 else()
507     set(all_objects=cells_obj)
508 end()
509
510 End()//end of checking for empty object listif(objects.@count>0)
511 End()
512 end() // end of the analysis of valid image fields
513 end() // end of the foreach loop over image fields
514
515
516 if (defined("all_objects") )
517 if (IN_ChansDAPI>0)
518
519     objectfilter(nucleus__intensity_dapi_intensity<IN_DAPIIntensitymax and
520 nucleus__intensity_dapi_intensity>100 and nucleus__morphology__NrArea2CytoplasmArea
521 <100 , objects=all_objects)
522     set(all_AnalyzedCells = objects)
523 Else()
524     set(all_AnalyzedCells = all_objects)
525 End()
526
527
528
529 //Write Single Cells Results to a file
530 if( all_AnalyzedCells.count>0 )
531     set(filename= DataPath & DataFileName)

```

```

532         if(writesinglecell)
533
534         OperaTemplates::WriteObjectData(objects=all_AnalyzedCells,out_filename=filename)
535         End()
536         //output the mean and std for all objects data
537         output(all_analyzedcells.count, "Total_cells_analyzed")
538         set(AttrNames=all_AnalyzedCells.keys)           // attributes of the current
539 object list
540         foreach(AttrNames)
541
542                                     set(a1=all_AnalyzedCells.[i])
543                                     if(a1.class=="vector" and
544 a1.class!="intervalvector" and a1.class!="indexvector" and a1.elemtype<8)
545                                     // the currently looked
546 at attribute is something we could output.
547                                     If(lower(i) != "row" and
548 lower(i) != "column" and lower(i) != "field")
549                                     set(attrn=i)
550
551                                     output(eval("all_analyzedcells." & attrn & ".mean"), attrn & "_mean")
552
553                                     output(eval("all_analyzedcells." & attrn & ".stddev"), attrn & "_stddev")
554                                     End()
555                                     end()
556         End()
557 End()//end of ( all_AnalyzedCells.@count>0 )
558 End()//end of if (defined("all_objects"))
559
560
561
562
563

```